

ANALYSIS OF CHINA'S EXPERIENCE IN ACCESSION TO THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION AND THE REFORMS AND EXPECTED CHANGES IN UZBEKISTAN'S ACCESSION PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the recent development indicators of Uzbekistan's economy and the reforms being implemented in the process of accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO). The 6.5 percent GDP growth in 2024, along with the reduction of budget and external account deficits, indicates the strengthening of economic stability. At the same time, inflation and global trade uncertainties are highlighted as major risk factors. The study evaluates the reduction of subsidies, the harmonization of customs and technical regulations with international standards, and the strengthening of intellectual property rights as processes consistent with WTO requirements. Based on China's experience, enhancing agricultural competitiveness is emphasized as a key challenge for Uzbekistan. WTO accession is scientifically justified as a factor that can contribute to sustainable growth through deepening liberalization in the national economy, creating equal conditions for the private sector, and strengthening competitiveness.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan's economy, World Trade Organization (WTO), economic reforms, subsidy reduction, trade liberalization, competitiveness, agriculture.*

Introduction

Uzbekistan's economy continues to develop at a strong pace. In 2024, real GDP growth amounted to 6.5 percent, which was supported by high domestic demand. The current account deficit decreased by 2.6 percentage points in 2024, falling to 5.0 percent of GDP. This was driven by strong remittances, high commodity prices, rapid growth in non-gold exports, and the completion of one-off imports in 2023. International reserves remain at a sufficient level. The consolidated state deficit (CSD) decreased by 1.7 percentage points in 2024, reaching 3.2 percent of GDP. This was achieved mainly through the reduction of energy subsidies and more targeted social spending, while high gold prices compensated for revenue losses due to increased VAT refunds. However, the smaller budget deficit led to weaker domestic demand, which was mitigated by increased spending from the broader public sector, including state-owned enterprises. This process was financed by raising the external borrowing limit. Inflation remains high: in March 2025, annual inflation stood at 10.3 percent. This was mainly the result of last year's necessary increases in energy tariffs and other administered prices, as well as their spillover effects on other prices.

Growth prospects remain strong, but external uncertainties are increasing. Rising global tariffs have heightened uncertainty and tightened global financial conditions. This could affect Uzbekistan through external demand, commodity prices, and financial flows. Nevertheless, according to baseline forecasts, real GDP growth in 2025 and 2026 is expected to be around 6 percent. Strong private consumption, investments, and continued structural reforms will be the

main drivers. The current account deficit is projected to remain at 5 percent of GDP in 2025. In this case, growth in gold exports and state sector consolidation will offset the weakening of non-gold exports due to sluggish growth among trading partners. Inflation is expected to be slightly above 8 percent year-on-year by the end of 2025 and to gradually decline in subsequent years as a result of strict macroeconomic and macroprudential policies, as well as structural reforms.

On June 13, 2025, the 10th Working Party meeting on Uzbekistan's accession to the World Trade Organization was held, during which discussions were held on what reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan and to what extent WTO rules have been implemented into national legislation. At this meeting, Deputy Prime Minister Jamshid Khodjayev stated that "Uzbekistan is going through a decisive stage in the process of WTO accession, that trade-distorting measures, uncertain restrictions, and rising protectionist sentiments are undermining confidence, slowing down economic growth, and weakening the stability and fairness of multilateral trade. From this point of view, Uzbekistan's commitment to the WTO — and its aspiration to build a modern, market-based economy relying on rules-based trade — has never been as strong as it is now."

Based on this view, the WTO remains the only reliable mechanism capable of ensuring a transparent, stable, and inclusive global trading system, and although doubts exist regarding the system's adaptability, in our opinion, any meaningful reform should not weaken its core functions but rather strengthen them. For nearly thirty years, the WTO has resolved disputes, opened markets, and supported economic development by strengthening fairness and discipline in international trade. As emphasized by the International Monetary Fund, Uzbekistan has now become a clear example of a transition economy where economic liberalization is increasingly supported by institutional reforms. Accession to the WTO is important to consolidate these achievements. Furthermore, this process will serve as external support for the remaining stages of transition, such as creating equal opportunities for the private sector, introducing corporate governance in state-owned enterprises, and privatization.

In the spirit of transformation, since 2023 Uzbekistan has taken concrete practical steps to accelerate its accession and has achieved the following results:

- Five working party meetings and several technical sessions were held on agriculture, technical barriers to trade (TBT), and sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) issues;
- More than 700 questions received from members were answered;
- Over 30 accession documents were submitted and more than 130 legal acts were aligned with WTO agreements;
- More than 200 bilateral market negotiations were conducted, and with 24 members negotiations were concluded, offering commercially significant commitments in goods and services.

Major reforms have also been implemented in the domestic market:

- Export-linked subsidies and non-transparent export restrictions were abolished;
- Exclusive rights of state-owned enterprises in the gas, electricity, and metals sectors were eliminated;
- Price controls were liberalized and privatization was accelerated;
- Advanced legislative harmonization was carried out under the TRIPS Agreement, and several major international intellectual property treaties were joined;
- Registration fees for domestic and foreign firms were equalized;
- The Customs Code was aligned with WTO valuation and trade facilitation rules;

- Technical and SPS systems are being harmonized with international standards, food safety is being strengthened, and trade barriers are being reduced.

These reforms, stemming from our core commitments, aim to transform Uzbekistan into a full-fledged market economy and also demonstrate that reforms are not only about promises but about the ability to deliver tangible results. It should be noted that Uzbekistan is successfully advancing through the multi-stage path of WTO accession and is actively studying the accession experience of neighboring WTO member states as well as developed countries.

In particular, China, the economic giant of Asia, became a member of the WTO on December 11, 2001. Before joining this organization, China underwent a 15-year negotiation period. Prior to accession, China undertook commitments to reduce average tariffs on agricultural products from 22% to 17%. Currently, China's average tariff level stands at 9.9% for all products and 15.6% for agricultural products. The main issue discussed in relation to China's agriculture was its subsidy policy. Within the framework of WTO accession, China retained the possibility of providing subsidies for agricultural products up to 8.5% of their value.

Before China's accession to the WTO, many experts predicted that its agriculture would suffer losses, since accession required reducing export subsidies and removing artificial barriers to agricultural imports. What actually happened will be concluded at the end of our analysis.

In the diagram below, we can see how China's GDP changed after joining the WTO.

Source: <https://data.worldbank.org/country/china?view=chart>

From the diagram above, we can see that China's GDP only increased during the years of WTO membership. If we compare the GDP size in 2001 and 2024, we can observe that China's GDP grew 13.7 times over this period. That is, in 2001, the initial year of WTO membership, China's GDP amounted to 1.36 trillion dollars, while by 2024 it had reached 18.74 trillion dollars. Meanwhile, during this period China's population increased only by 1.1 times. This shows that during the years of WTO membership, China's GDP grew at a much faster pace relative to its population. Now, through the following table, we will examine how China's foreign trade developed during the years of WTO membership.

It is no secret that today China is the world's second-largest economy after the United States. At the same time, the country's WTO membership has not only provided opportunities to other countries but also intensified competition in the international arena. The liberalization of the economy through WTO membership has had a very positive impact on China's economy. Although the overall volume of agricultural products increased, imports of agricultural products also grew. In China's agricultural imports, grain crops, vegetables and fruits, oils, and raw

materials for light industry account for the largest share. In agricultural exports, however, products that are processed and have higher added value hold a greater share.

At present, the main problem in global agricultural trade is that developing countries are forced to compete with the subsidized agricultural products of developed countries. The largest economies — such as the European Union, the United States, Japan, and South Korea — allocate hundreds of billions of dollars annually to agricultural subsidies. In turn, this causes serious damage to the agriculture of developing countries that have entered into free trade. China does not have such a well-established subsidy system as these countries. However, as a developing country, China has the right to subsidize up to 10 percent of its agricultural production volume, while this figure is limited to 5 percent in developed countries. Yet, upon accession, China retained the right to subsidize up to 8.5 percent.

The Chinese government supports trade liberalization, meaning it favors reducing various obstacles to trade such as subsidies and sanitary measures. By studying China's WTO accession experience and the changes in its agriculture within this framework, we can conclude that when our country joins this organization, our agricultural sector will face serious challenges. That is, our agriculture will have to compete with subsidized foreign agricultural products, which will in turn put our domestic producers in a difficult situation. Furthermore, not only subsidies but also their highly technological, science-based agricultural system gives them an advantage over our agriculture, which still largely relies on traditional practices. Within the framework of WTO membership, we must begin addressing these problems now, and we should also start implementing systematic measures to provide employment in other sectors for the large number of people currently engaged in agriculture who may lose their jobs after accession.

Another important aspect that should be taken into account is that the International Monetary Fund, in order to identify macro-indicator dynamics, trends, and risk factors for the years 2022–2026 and to provide practical conclusions for policy, presented the following facts and projected indicators.

Uzbekistan: Selected Economic Indicators, 2022-2026

	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
			Est.	Proj.	Proj.
National income					
Real GDP growth (percent change)	6.0	6.3	6.5	5.9	5.8
Nominal GDP (in trillions of Sum)	996	1,204	1,455	1,733	2,005
GDP per capita (in U.S. dollars)	2,555	2,849	3,113	3,487	3,805
Population (in millions)	35.3	36.0	36.9	37.7	38.5
Prices					
		(Percent change)			
Consumer price inflation (end of period)	12.3	8.7	9.8	8.4	6.5
GDP deflator	14.5	13.8	13.3	12.5	9.4
External sector					
		(Percent of GDP)			
Current account balance	-3.2	-7.6	-5.0	-5.0	-4.8
External debt	49.2	54.5	57.2	55.8	55.5
		(Level)			
Exchange rate (in sums per U.S. dollar; end of period)	11,225	12,339	12,920
Real effective exchange rate (ave. 2015 = 100, decline = depreciation)	61.8	58.8	55.4
Government finance					
		(Percent of GDP)			
Consolidated budget revenues	28.8	26.7	26.5	26.3	26.4
Consolidated budget expenditures	32.4	31.6	29.7	29.3	29.4
Consolidated budget balance	-3.6	-4.9	-3.2	-3.0	-3.0
Adjusted revenues 1/	27.7	25.9	25.5	25.3	25.5
Adjusted expenditures 1/	31.3	29.9	27.8	27.3	27.8
Adjusted fiscal balance	-3.7	-4.0	-2.3	-2.0	-2.3
Policy-based lending	0.0	0.9	0.9	1.0	0.7
Overall fiscal balance 1/	-3.6	-4.9	-3.2	-3.0	-3.0
Public debt	30.5	32.2	32.6	33.3	33.2
Money and credit					
		(Percent Change)			
Reserve money	31.4	4.9	9.5	9.2	8.8
Broad money	30.2	12.2	30.6	19.4	16.3
Credit to the economy	21.4	23.2	14.0	19.3	16.0

Sources: Country authorities; and IMF staff estimates.

1/ IMF staff adjusts budget revenues and expenditures for financing operations, such as equity injections, and policy lending.

Source: Uzbekistan: Staff Concluding Statement of the 2025 Article IV Mission

From this table, we can see that Uzbekistan's projected main macroeconomic indicators for 2022–2026 are closely linked with the reforms undertaken in the process of joining the World Trade Organization (WTO). According to the International Monetary Fund, real gross domestic product (GDP) growth during this period is expected to average around 6 percent. This figure indicates that stable growth rates are being maintained in the national economy. Trade liberalization and improvements in the investment climate during the WTO accession process are considered key factors supporting this sustainable growth.

Per capita GDP is projected to rise from USD 2,555 in 2022 to USD 3,805 in 2026, reflecting an increase in the country's socio-economic well-being. The competitive environment required by the WTO and adaptation to international market standards may, in the long run, contribute to further increases in real household incomes.

Price stability is also directly connected with reforms in the WTO accession process. According to the table, the inflation rate is projected to decline from 12.3 percent in 2022 to 6.5 percent in 2026. This process is explained by the tightening of monetary policy and the gradual reduction of certain subsidies. Within the framework of WTO membership, the obligation to regulate subsidies ensures that price mechanisms in the country are formed on the basis of market principles.

At the same time, the external trade balance is one of the most significant challenges associated with WTO-related reforms. According to forecasts, the current account deficit stood at -7.6 percent of GDP in 2023, but in subsequent years this indicator is expected to narrow slightly (to -4.8 percent). The expansion of imports and fluctuations in external demand are the main factors behind the deficit. As a result of WTO accession, the reduction of customs tariffs and non-

tariff barriers may further intensify this process in the short term. However, in the long term, export diversification and wider access to international markets will help reduce the deficit.

Fiscal indicators are also being shaped in line with WTO requirements. The consolidated budget deficit is projected to decline from -3.6 percent in 2022 to around -3 percent in 2026, indicating the implementation of fiscal consolidation policy. Under WTO membership, since state support cannot be excessively expanded, ensuring fiscal discipline will become even more relevant. Maintaining public debt below 30 percent of GDP shows that macroeconomic stability remains within a relatively safe range.

In terms of monetary indicators, the flow of credit into the economy is expected to continue growing. The WTO accession process requires liberalization of financial markets and strengthening of competition. This can contribute to more efficient allocation of credit, particularly toward sectors that support exports and create high added value.

In conclusion, the economic forecasts for 2022–2026 show that the reforms carried out during Uzbekistan's WTO accession process are reflected in the macroeconomic indicators. The sustainability of real growth and the decline in inflation demonstrate adaptation to market mechanisms in line with WTO requirements. However, the trade balance deficit and high external debt remain major challenges even under WTO conditions. Therefore, Uzbekistan's priority tasks should include export diversification, adaptation to international standards, and effective management of external financial flows.

Conclusions and Recommendations. Uzbekistan's long road to the WTO was prolonged due to the slow pace of market reforms. In response to external shocks, the country chose protectionism. While protectionist policy had certain advantages during times of economic crisis, overall it imposed high costs because it prevented deep market reforms. Foreign trade remained restricted, and the country's attractiveness for foreign direct investment was lower than that of the rest of the region. However, with the change in leadership, there is optimism about the ongoing reforms. WTO membership could bring Uzbekistan greater benefits compared to other former Soviet Union states. Uzbekistan is more economically closed and ranks lowest among regional countries in terms of FDI inflows per capita. Lowering import tariffs will give consumers greater choice, and improved legal and institutional frameworks could increase investment flows. Most importantly, WTO membership will make it possible to advance market reforms further, making reversal difficult if not impossible. Given Uzbekistan's history of reforms followed by protectionism, the risk of reversal cannot be completely ruled out. Therefore, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Expedite negotiations on WTO accession;
- Reduce import tariffs to ensure competition in domestic markets;
- Improve foreign trade and investment legislation in line with international standards;
- External partners should strongly support Uzbekistan's trade policy reforms and, if necessary, provide technical and financial assistance;
- Trade policy reform and Uzbekistan's WTO accession should be reflected in external partners' political documents (for example, in the European Union's strategy toward Central Asia).

WTO accession is of great importance for Uzbekistan to advance market reforms and make them irreversible. With an open, transparent, and developing economy, Uzbekistan will become even more attractive for international business after joining the WTO.

REFERENCES

1. Pomfret, Richard. 2020. “O‘zbekiston va Jahon savdo tashkiloti”. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> ga qarang. 2(1): 54–61. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16997/srjed.35>
2. A Akhrorjon. (2022). Reasons, problems and consequences for the accession of the Uzbek economy to the WTO. International scientific conference "Topical issues of the economy in modern society"
3. A Abdullaev. (2022). O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyoti uchun jstga a’zo bo‘lish sabab muammo va natijalari. Raqamli texnologiyalar va ta’lim istiqbollari 1 (2), 113-121
4. A Akhrorjon, K Zumradkhan. (2022). The impact and results of membership of the wto on the education system. Educational Research in Universal Sciences 1 (5), 24-32
5. China Business Review (2000) ‘WTO Special Report: The Real Work Begins’, China Business Review, 27: 17–62.
6. Deckers, Wolfgang (2004) ‘China, Globalisation and the World Trade Organisation’, Journal of Contemporary Asia, 34(1): 102–19.
7. Fukusaku, K. and Wall, D. (1994) China’s Long March to an Open Economy, Paris: Development Centre of the OECD.
8. Lai, H. H. (2001) ‘Behind China’s World Trade Organization Agreement with the USA’, Third World Quarterly, 22(2): 237–55
9. <https://www.worldbank.org/>
10. <https://www.wto.org/>
11. <https://www.imf.org/>